

PRIORITY BASED LOAD SHEDDING AND AUTOMATIC POWER FACTOR CORRECTION

MR. SANTOSH KASHID

Department of Electrical Engineering, Solapur University / SKNSCOE Pandharpur, India
sgkashid@gmail.com

MISS. KIRAN DEVKATE

Department of Electrical Engineering, Solapur University / SKNSCOE Pandharpur, India
kiranrdevkate@gmail.com

MISS. KIRAN KAMBLE

Department of Electrical Engineering, Solapur University / SKNSCOE Pandharpur, India
kirankamble4343@gmail.com

MR. SUNIL JADHAV

Department of Electrical Engineering, Solapur University / SKNSCOE Pandharpur, India
suniljadhav.0902@gmail.com

MR. MAHESH PAWAR

Department of Electrical Engineering, Solapur University / SKNSCOE Pandharpur, India
maheshpawar098@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In power system, the main issue is power quality and load management. Most of commercial and industrial loads are inductive in nature causes lagging power factor. The improvement of power factor is important for industrial as well as domestic area. By using APFC panel we can overcome the lagging power factor problem. The designing of load priority is the combination of both random and fixed priority. This is used to achieve optimal load shedding.

KEY WORDS: Power factor, APFC, Capacitor bank, Load shedding, Priority, Arduino.

INTRODUCTION

Electrical power system is the major source to provide energy to use for residential, commercial, industrial and agricultural purposes. Now days the demand of power is increasing day by day. The difference between demand and supply causes consumers to suffer from the unwanted load shedding. Also the quality of power is poor because of heavy industrialisation. Which causes heavy losses in power system.

Power factor is most important constraint in power system. Were apparent, active and reactive power are three forms of power .were apparent power is total power supplied by the load.Active power is power consumed by the load and reactive power is power which drawn as by the passive element such capacitor and inductor .this is causes due less efficient use of electrical equipment's. To compensate this capacitor bank can be added into the system and up to sufficient limit we can improve the power factor of the system [1].

Due to poor and inefficient power use the harmonics currents in the utility. It is very well known that these harmonic currents causes several problems such as unstable, increasing heat,noise and reduce the capability of the line to provide the energy.

Also the priority based load shedding will help us to improve the system stability and reliability .highest priority consumers will be feed continuously and low priority consumers will get disconnected from the system [2].

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Load control provides an effective means of alleviating voltage collapse. For example the cascading failure of the North American power system in august 2003 could have been avoided by tripping a relatively small amount of load in the Cleveland [3]. An electrical load that operates on the ac power requires the apparent power, which consists of teal power plus reactive power. The presence of reactive power causes the real power to be less than the apparent power and so the electric load has power factor less than one. The cascading failure of the system will collapse the system and complete shutdown will take place. But priority based load shedding will help to avoid such conditions [4].

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure no 1: Block Diagram of APFC and PBLs.

WORKING PRINCIPLE

To avoid the crises in power system, we have to follow the following two methods. Which will help to improve the power system stability.

One method is to improve power quality. It can be improved by use of capacitor bank. Normally the source provides the apparent power to the transmission lines distribution network and the load centres which is given by

$$S=VI$$

The power consumed by the load is said active power. Which is mathematically given by

$$P=VI\cos\phi$$

In kW. Reactive power is another power which continuously flows in the circuit in opposition to apparent power .which causes the active power became less than the apparent power .it is given by

$$Q= VI\sin\phi$$

Which is measured in kVAR.

The power factor of the system should be unity which is an ideal condition. It is possible when there is only purely resistive load on the network. But such condition never comes because about 90% of load is an industrial load and which consists heavy inductive loads. Such as compressors, arc furnaces, induction

motors etc. Mostly inductive load causes to poor power factor .by improving power factor we can improve the system efficiency.

We can improve the power factor by using capacitor bank. In this project we are design the system which can add the capacitor automatically according the load condition .if the power factor of the system is unity then no capacitor is going to add in the circuit, but if the power factor is lagging then microcontroller calculate the phase difference between the voltage and the current and simultaneously adds the capacitor. Hence the power factor of system get improves [5].

Automatic load shedding is another option to compensate the demand. When the generating power is less than the demand then low priority loads will get automatically disconnected from the circuit. This will help to manage the demand and supply. To manage the load shedding we had used the arduino 2560 that sense the power consumption of overall system. To limit the power and the priorities of the load to maintain the consumption [6].

RESULT

Capacitor Size Calculation

1. First step is to determine current (old) KVA and PF.

Current power factor $p.f_1 = 0.89$.

Current Choke KW = 40W.

2. Then to calculate KVA

Reactive Power KVA = KW / $p.f_1$.

$KVA_1 = 40 / 0.89 = 44.94$ VA

3. Current KVAR of system

$KVAR_1 = [KVA_1^2 - KW^2]^{1/2}$

$KVAR_1 = 20.5$ VAR

4. Desire power factor of system

Desire power factor $p.f_2 = 0.97$

5. New KVA for desire power factor

$KVA_2 = 40 / 0.97 = 41.23$ VA

6. New KVAR

$KVAR_2 = [KVA_2^2 - KW^2]^{1/2}$

$KVAR_2 = 10$ VAR

7. KVAR of the capacitor to be installed is

$KVAR_{cap} = KVAR_1 - KVAR_2$

$KVAR_{cap} = 10.5$ VAR

8. Capacitor in Farads

$C = KVAR_{cap} / (2\pi fV^2)$

$C = 10.5 / (2 * \pi * 50 * 400^2)$

$C = 2.0889 * 10^{-3}$ F

The nearest standard size would be installed, probably 2.5 MFD.

Here we take the value of time difference between voltage and current by converting them to pulse the value of count1 and value of count2. This will give ratio between time gap and time period [7]. And angle is calculated as

$$\text{Angle} = (\text{count2} / \text{count1}) / 360.$$

$$\text{Power Factor} = \cos(\text{Angle}).$$

FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

The priority based load shedding can be used for industrial load management by formulation utilizes integer programming technique for minimizing the electricity costs. The load management can change the cost cure of electricity bill and demand management [8], [9].

CONCLUSION

The system is able to analyse priority of load and power available to distribute among the load on basis of priority and requirement of load. On basic data of power availability system monitor the load shedding. With load management system also improve the power factor of load to reduce losses [10].

Photograph no 2: APFC and PBLs.

REFERENCE

- I. Oscar García, Member, IEEE, José A. Cobos, Member, IEEE, Roberto Prieto, Member, IEEE, Pedro Alou, and Javier Uceda, Senior Member, IEEE, "Single Phase Power Factor Correction: A Survey." IEEE Transactions On Power Electronics, Vol. 18, No. 3, May 2003.
- II. J. A. Laghari, Hazlie Mokhlis, Member, IEEE, Mazaher Karimi, Member, IEEE, Abdul Halim Abu Bakar, Member, IEEE, and Hasmani Mohamad, Member, IEEE, "A New Frequency Load Shedding Technique Bases on Combination of Fixed and Random Priority of Loads for Smart Grid Applications." IEEE Transactions On Power System, No. October 2014.
- III. I. A. Hiskens, B. Gong, Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Wisconsin - Madison, USA, "MPC-Based Load Shedding for Voltage Stability Enhancement." 44th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control, and the European Control Conference 2005, Seville, Spain, December 12-15, 2005.
- IV. Mr. A Kumar Tiwari, "Automatic Power Factor Correction Using Capacitive Bank." Int Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, ISSN : 2248-9622, Vol. 4, Issue 2(Version 1), No. February 2014.
- V. Aparna Sarkar, M-Tech Student, Umesh Hiwase, Asst. Professor, Priyadarshini College of Engineering, Nagpur, "Automatic Power Factor Correction By Continuous Monitoring." Int Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT), ISSN : 2277-3754, Vol. 4, Issue 10, April 2015.

- VI. Isaac Frampton, Senior Staff Engineer at Kohler Co. Power System Division, "Power Up With A Load Management System : Setting Up A Load-Mangement System." Power System Topic 110, Part 3 of a 3-Part Series.
- VII. Pranjali Sonje, Pursuing MTech, Anagha Soman, Assistent Professor, Bharati Vidyapeeth University college of Engineeriing, Pune, "Power Factor Correction Using PIC Microcontroller." Int Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT), ISSN : 2277-3754, Vol. 3, Issue 4, October 2013.
- VIII. S. Ashok, M-Tech from IIT Delhi, Rangan Banerjee, B-Tech and Ph.D. from IIT Bombay, "An Optimization Mode For Industrial Load Management." IEEE Transactions On Power System, Vol. 16, No. 4, November 2001.
- IX. Peter Palensky, Senior Member, IEEE, Dietmar Dietrich, Senior Member, IEEE, "Demand Side Management : Demand Response, Intelligent Energy System and Smart Loads." IEEE Transactions On Industrial Informatics, Vol. 7, No. 3, August 2011.
- X. Mr. Akash Sakpal, Mr. Shubham Salunkhe, Mr. Subodh Sonawane, Prof. Mrs. A. A. Rane, Electrical Aissms, Ioit, Pune, "Automatic Power Factor Correction By Using Controller." IJARIE, ISSN(O)-2395-4396, Vol. 2, Issue-3 2016.